

FROM BROWN-FIELDS TO INNOVATION DISTRICTS: A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH TO SUSTAINABILITY

L. Biancuzzo

PAU Department, Università degli Studi Mediterranea di Reggio Calabria, Salita Melissari, 92124, Reggio Calabria, Italy

Email: laura.biancuzzo@unirc.it

Abstract: In the globalisation era, the future of older industrial cities will result from their expertise on investing into their underutilised assets in order to keep being competitive globally; it is therefore necessary to revitalise the land known as brown-field. An emerging urban model, the innovation district, puts forward ground breaking promises about its ability to cope with this specific challenge, standing as a driver for a sustainable and inclusive economic development. This paper aims to show the degree to which innovation is effective in giving a meaningful response to brown-field problems, first by considering a conceptual framework to assess the comprehensive approach aimed at improving the social, economic and physical issues inherent to post-industrial landscapes; then by testing it through empirical research work. To support the discussion with evidence, the Boston Innovation District case study will be investigated, pointing out the policies and planning initiatives undertaken in the Seaport area. Findings from this research highlight the innovative-led approach effectiveness in matching all the issues considered as relevant to sustainable brown-fields redevelopment, and useful lessons can be drawn in encouraging planners and policy-makers towards considering the role of innovation in urban regeneration initiatives targeting distressed areas.

Keywords: Brown-field Redevelopment, Innovation District, Local Economic Development, Sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deindustrialisation has left tangible traces on the territorial geography; thus, some of the areas where once vital industries used to thrive have been replaced by brown-fields (Bartsch & Collaton 1997). Nowadays, a wide consensus exists on the need to take actions - targeted at revitalising the stagnant economy in these distressed markets, while restoring a safer and uncontaminated urban environment, and ensuring environmental justice (Dernbach 1998; Ruthl 1998), within broader smart growth policies which promote compact development and land consumption reduction (Greenberg et al. 2001). Although several research studies attempted to face the challenge of how to plan, manage and assess brown-fields redevelopment complying with the principles of sustainability (Boer 1995; EPA 2015; RESCUE 2003), less emphasis has been placed on the potential key role of innovation, despite its recognised ability to foster economic growth (Katz & Wagner 2014). This paper puts the body of knowledge forward on the nexus between brown-field regeneration and innovation, by analysing the capability of the newly conceived “re-imagined urban areas” model to achieve the objectives of sustainable brown-field redevelopment. To do that, the paper investigates the Boston Innovation District case study, by focusing on the implementation process of the innovation-led strategy undertaken by the Boston Redevelopment Authority (BRA). Accordingly, the planning initiative sought to guide economic, social and physical changes in the Seaport area in order to create a neighbourhood consistent with the highly innovative Boston’s environment. This paper is organised in five

parts. Following this introduction, it provides a scientific background through an overview of theoretical approaches to brown-field redevelopment and prevailing assessment methodologies in terms of sustainability, introducing the concept of innovation in the sustainable development context. In the third part, the methodology that determined the objectives of each dimension for the sustainability assessment model is presented, followed by the description of the case study. Next, the Boston Innovation District achievements are analysed, and how these outcomes might affect the further planning practices is discussed. Finally, findings and conclusions are presented in the fifth part.

2. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

This paper aims to present one of the most common phenomenon lately facing communities in the Western countries: the land classified as brown-field, focusing on the outcomes of its regeneration process. Three issues of the growing literature, dealing with the abovementioned area of concern, focused on the United States perspective, make a significant contribution to the understanding of the topic: (1) the literature exploring the reasons brown-field regeneration is considered a strategy for local economic development, (2) studies examining the innovation district urban model as a powerful driver for a sustainable economic development, and (3) the literature attempting to assess the impacts of brown-field reclamation in heading towards sustainability.

2.1 Brown-field Redevelopment as a Local Economic Development Strategy

To set the context between brown-field redevelopment and urban regeneration, a preliminary investigation of the process which led to the creation of derelict land and sites is presented. Over the past few decades, the great economic powers, Europe and the United States, have experienced considerable processes of change in terms of spatial, social, environmental and economic arrangement. The glorious days of several industrial cities came to an end when the reallocation of many factories to foreign countries started the process of deindustrialisation. Even more significant in the context of globalisation, industrial activities have undergone substantial changes due to a shift from manufacturing to service economies, which has resulted in the downsizing of enterprises as well as the complete loss of whole production industries. These significant transformations have left tangible traces on the territorial geography; thus, some of the areas where once vital industries used to thrive have been replaced by vacant and most likely polluted land, strongly affecting the citizens who live close to them (Bartsch & Collaton 1997; Olivier et al. 2005; Adams et al. 2009). These sites are known as brown-fields. While individual nations hold independent definitions of brown-field sites, the American context commonly refers to “abandoned or underutilised industrial and commercial facilities where expansion or redevelopment is complicated by real or perceived contamination” (Knox & McCarthy 2012). In addition, “The Environmental Protection Agency estimates the number of brown-fields located in the U.S. to be between 500,000 and 1,000,000” (EPA 2012).

Given the impressive figures, the presence of brown-field sites across the country represents a significant urban management problem; additionally, it has been documented that beyond the scale and spatial configuration, the existence of brown-fields has multiple adverse effects, not only over the environment, but also on the economic and social health of an entire region (COBRAMAN 2009). These sites have been held up as “blights of the neighbourhoods, able

of discouraging economic development and undermining local [government] tax bases” (Preston 2003); moreover, they often serve as gathering sites for the downtrodden citizens of a community, which inevitably leads to neighbourhoods in greater decline in pure economic terms (Sirmans & Macpherson 2003). Beside the economic and societal impacts, the concept of brown-field as an environmental issue has to be highlighted, due to the increasing number of abandoned areas with real or plausible hazardous contamination, representing a heartfelt public concern.

As a consequence of the afore mentioned reasons, in the last decades, federal, state, and local governments redirected their priorities to regenerate unproductive lands. As a matter of fact, brown-fields redevelopment is considered the preferable method to fight the decaying phenomenon of core inner urban areas, enhancing the quality of inner cities environments (Dixon et al. 2010); and a powerful smart growth policy which promotes compact development and significantly reduces land consumption (Greenberg et al. 2001). In support of this, it has been demonstrated that “putting clean land back into productive use brings with it a range of social and economic benefits that will strengthen those communities for years to come” (EPA 2015) by providing a remarkable opportunity for the redevelopment of the social equity, economic stability, and environmental equilibrium. Traditionally, brown-fields remediation results in a deep community economic revitalisation and job creation, significant neighbourhood restoration, not to mention the meaningful reduction of the development pressures on green-fields through the reuse of urban space (PCSD 1998). Moreover, cleaning up abandoned industrial sites leads to a twofold advantage in terms of economic opportunities and investments: on the one hand, the private sector benefits from the convenient chance to purchase properties at below market price and make profits thanks to the financial and technical assistance they obtain to clean them up; on the other hand, state and local governments create economic viability through a variety of financial incentives and fiscal exemptions which facilitates and accelerates the development process (Verbit 2001).

However, for years now, brown-fields run up against the increasing scepticism towards the revitalisation of neglected sites; strict environmental and economic policies are commonly considered to be a major barrier to redevelopment, combined with the expensiveness of assessment and rehabilitation practices, and the difficult management of such a significant scope projects (BenDor & Metcalf 2005). To overcome these obstacles, it is worth evaluating to what extent brown-field redevelopment programs “pay for themselves” by generating economic (jobs, wages, increases in property values) and fiscal (increased tax revenues without increasing tax rates) benefits (Frank 2014). The attempted literature highlights the potentially remarkable results of investments in the distressed areas, as emphasised by the United States Conference of Mayors report (2008), which provided data relative to a compilation of a questionnaire responded by more than 200 US cities - belonging to more than 41 different states - that have been involved in a brown-field redevelopment project. The cities were asked to identify the four most important benefits as a result of the regeneration: neighbourhood revitalisation was the most frequently cited benefit, along with job creation, and an increase in city’s tax base and environmental protection. On the same line, the Chicago Metropolitan Agency for Planning (2008) gives credit to the wide-ranging benefits of bringing a site back to active use, focussing on the opportunity for businesses to thrive creating new jobs and attracting private investments. In sum, a single site intervention entails remarkable spill-over effects on the quality of life for people living in neighbourhoods with brown-field sites and on the economy of the entire region (Chilton et al. 2008).

2.2 Innovation Districts: a driver for a sustainable economic development

One sound argument in response to the challenge of post industrial sites comes from a new urban and economic redevelopment strategy: the creation of innovation districts. Innovation districts have been considered an emerging urban model, a product of the shift in the spatial geography of innovation occurred over the last few years in several cities and metropolitan areas in the United States and other countries (Feldman 1994). A growing number of talented workers and innovative firms chose to move from the spatially isolated suburban corridors - places best exemplified by the Silicon Valley in the San Francisco Bay Area - and cluster spatially in compact and more desirable areas in the inner city; at the same time, an increasing share of citizens is drawn to these districts, given the shifted location preferences toward more vibrant and amenity rich places to live and work (Audretsch & Feldman 2003).

The purposes behind the rise of innovation districts are clear: to create a dynamic place where entrepreneurs and knowledge-intensive businesses can share ideas, and benefit from the impact of proximity on learning and knowledge spill overs, increasing their competitive advantage (Boschma 2005). Nevertheless, the trend is still recent and, lacks a univocal definition due to its multi-dimensional nature. As stated in the influential Brookings Institution report, edited by Bruce Katz and Julie Wagner (2014), the term innovation district is mostly used to identify “geographic areas physically compact, transit-accessible, and technically-wired where leading- edge anchor institutions and companies cluster and connect with start-ups, business incubators, and accelerators. They also offer mixed use housing, office, and retail.” As the afore mentioned explanation suggests, these districts perfectly embody the comprehensive concept of “cityness” coined by Saskia Sassen (1991): the complex intersection of differences embedded in these urban spaces produces something new; proximity and density, together with diversity of people, subcultures, practices, lead to innovation indeed. The affirmation of this concept is translated into reality in “new or improved ideas, products, services, technologies, or processes creating new market demand or cutting-edge solutions to economic, social and environmental challenges” (Katz & Wagner 2014).

Additionally, innovation district urban forms and functions cannot be defined a priori; given their ability to leverage the economic strengths of the specific metropolitan area in which they locate, they significantly vary by type and size, but also differ in specializations for growth - some of them slant toward life sciences, while others are focused on the information technology sector or different highly creative industries (Read 2016). Whether the districts have been strategically planned or represent the spontaneous response to the market forces, they all contain a powerful and unique combination of economic, physical, and networking assets (see Figure 30) which, brought together in geographic proximity, stimulate the idea generation facilitating the entrepreneurial activity (Giuffrida et al. 2015).

Economic Assets	firms, institutions and relationships and social ties that connect employees and institutions	i) innovation drivers
Networking Assets	relationships and social ties that connect employees and institutions	i) strong ties ii) weak ties
Physical Assets	relationships and social ties that connect employees and institutions	i) spaces in the public realm ii) spaces in the private realm iii) assets that join spaces together

^A Figure 30: Common Features of Innovation Districts (Author's elaboration based on Katz & Wagner 2014)

All of these

observations highlight how this new approach to economic development takes place. Under the assumption that innovation districts have the unique capabilities to foster an inclusive and sustainable economic development, they contribute to address three of the modern-day plagues: the stagnant economy of the post recession period, the growing inequality that is damaging today's social structure, and the environmental threat due to the extensive sprawl. To this end, the most convincing line of evidence supporting this theory, are observations drawn from the "re-imagined urban areas", one of the three general models of District (Katz & Wagner 2014; Montini 2014). Accordingly, historic waterfronts and de-industrialised areas are the subject of physical and economic transformations charting a new path of innovative growth (Clark & Moonen 2015).

2.3 Assessing the Sustainability of Brown-field Redevelopment

As the first sub-section suggests, brown-field land use strategies clearly fit in the sustainability paradigm; brown-field revitalisation became one of the main issues to take into account to achieve a sustainable development indeed (Boer 1995; Dorsey 2003). On this matter, the number of references the literature makes is relevant, as demonstrated by the several federal agencies' initiatives targeted at the promotion of brown-fields "sustainable reuse" (EPA 2015). These actions aim for economic growth in the distressed property market, while improving the living conditions of neighbouring residents - as known as environmental justice communities, extremely affected by economic, social and environmental inequalities. (Dernbach 1998; Ruthl 1998).

Although the idea of sustainable development has significantly changed over the past decades and it can be defined in many ways, broad consensus is reached on the triple bottom line framework (Elkington 1998). The comprehensive approach rests therefore on "three pillars: economic growth, social progress and protection of the environment and natural resources"(Annan 2002), representing the core of the sustainability vision of the widely cited Brundtland report (WCED 1987) that refers to the potential of meeting the "needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." A particularly important milestone in the attempt of translating the sustainability concept into a "solid basis for decision making at all levels" (Capello & Nijkamp 2002), was the drafting of two documents: the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (United Nations 1992b) and the Agenda 21 (United Nations 1992a); within the afore mentioned, a well structured framework has been defined, providing recommended actions and detailed activities the governments should undertake in order to achieve sustainable development practices, accordingly to the desired performances. From then on, several frameworks have been developed in the attempt of providing an exhaustive assessment of the sustainability

threefold component, but not without disputes over the choice and suitability of the aspects to be covered and their proper calculation (Huetting & Reijnders 2004).

However, in order to point out the uniqueness of a brown-field redevelopment effort, distinguishing it from a conventional urban redevelopment initiative, it is deemed necessary to properly define a sustainable brown-field redevelopment process as “the management, rehabilitation and return to beneficial use of brown-fields in such a manner as to ensure the attainment and continued satisfaction of human needs for present and future generations in environmentally sensitive, economically viable, institutionally robust and socially acceptable ways within the particular regional context” (RESCUE 2003). The complex combination of planning policies, public and private initiatives, diverse stakeholder interests and technical skills, have an impact not only on the implementation process, but above all on the sustainability of the outcomes.

In support of the findings raised above, a great deal of uncertainty, regarding the measurement of the intended and unintended spill over effects of brown-fields regeneration, generated an impressive theoretical debate on the construction of sustainability frameworks in order to manage and assess the revitalisation of distressed areas. Some authors claim that, to successfully achieve a sustainable brown-field development, the holistic principle of sustainability has to be embedded in the entire process. One sound argument in support of this theory comes from the Model Framework devised by the Environmental Protection Agency (1999), that aims at guiding the stakeholders to properly structure the planning and development process, in order to direct their efforts towards a viable and sustainable brown-field redevelopment. Nijkamp et al. (2002) likewise propose a qualitative impact assessment model to provide a detailed description of the procedures to be followed, ensuring the critical success factors for a sustainable brownfield rehabilitation. According to this train of thought, the Redevelopment Assessment Framework provides a procedure that “informs stakeholders about the sustainability performance in a practical way” (Pediaditi et al. 2005) guaranteeing that sustainability is addressed and monitored across the life cycle of a brown-field site. Other scholars consider the evaluation a priori crucial to fulfil the sustainable brown-field development objectives. Specifically, the adoption of a decision-support system is seen as crucial to significantly reduce the uncertainties and the complex decision making process concerning the sustainability values of different land use scenarios for brown-fields. The computer-based module proposed by Bleicher & Gross (2010) deals precisely with this theory, as well as the approach chosen by Schädler et al. (2011). According to these assessment methods, through a comparative analysis of alternative brown-field rehabilitation options, the degree of sustainability is calculated, and the optimal redevelopment option is chosen. Still other authors place the emphasis on the methodology to be applied in order to measure the performance of brown-field regeneration processes according to sustainability principles. In this regard, the Principle - Criteria - Indicators framework approach describes the attempt to capture the complexity of the measurement starting from the definition of the three main sustainability dimensions, moving to the identification of specific objectives that have to be assessed through properly chosen indicators (Worrall et al. 2009). The Sustainability Assessment Tool is another good illustration of a three steps methodology which provides a wide range of qualitative and quantitative criteria to evaluate how sustainable a brown-field regeneration project is, on the basis of objectives, indicators and best practices (Franz et al. 2006). Accordingly, the framework built by Sardinha et al. (2013) consists in validating the achievement of six sustainability dimensions - environmental reconversion, cultural regeneration, social revalorisation, economic revitalisation, community reinforcement and strategic reframing - through the identification and application of some

categories for action. Furthermore, the measurement of sustainability is in many cases subject to a preliminary and well structured selection of indicators. This practice is well exemplified by the indicator based approach, applied by Hemphill et al. (2004), where the complex procedure of choosing the potentially relevant indicators is broken down into rigorous steps and followed by a points scoring phase, ensuring a comprehensive and transferable framework to quantify the sustainability of brown-fields revitalisation. Other researchers apply a similar methodology to select indicators capable of measuring the brown-field redevelopment success in terms of environment-health, finance, livability, and social-economic sustainability through a partially automated tool (Wedding & Crawford-Brown 2007), while still others consider the definition of economic and environmental performance indicators instrumental for measuring the unequivocal recognition of the sustainability achievements (Bacot 2006).

Despite the above mentioned debates, it appears commonly recognised that sustainability calls for context sensitive evaluation criteria, given its strict reliance on temporal, spatial and thematic context; thus, the selection of the most appropriate indicators lie with the local stakeholders and are tailored to reflect the site specific situation (Franz & Nathanail 2005; Olsson 2009). Hence, the local context dictates the specific sustainability needs, as defined by the local authorities and decision-makers' expectations. This implies that, on the one hand the stakeholders involved in the land reuse play a key role in the sustainability achievements, having a direct impact on whether the development is sustainable (Williams & Dair 2007); on the other hand, it determines the impossibility to apply a standardised list of indicators to measure "some unspecified type of sustainability brownfields" (Bleicher & Gross 2010).

In sum, while evaluating the current state of the art for the body of knowledge reviewed, it became clear that innovation, through the "re-imagined urban areas" model in particular, is potentially able to give a meaningful response to the problems shown by de-industrialised areas, leveraging the assets already present within the existing city limits. However, a gap in research about the nexus between brown-field and innovation district multiple positive effects (over the environment, on the economic and social health of the entire region) has been found. This paper puts forward the application of an objective-led framework designed to assess the sustainability of brown-fields development in order to capture the above mentioned relationship.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the light of the findings raised above, the inclination to measure brown-fields redevelopment sustainability according to specific indicators is quite misleading. A better understanding of the innovation multiple response can be achieved by approaching the research from a more comprehensive perspective, thus, by taking into consideration criteria that illustrate the general values recognised by the society.

The objectives-led approach adopted by Williams & Dair (2007) provides a framework broad enough to embrace the diverse contexts of brown-field redevelopment and the multidimensionality of impacts. It allows the author to effectively assess the sustainable development in the context of land reuse through a better insight of cause and effect; in addition, it also leads to the derivation of general principles from it, since it facilitates the transposition of abstract concepts - such as economic, social and environmental sustainability, into tangible practices. According to the method, all the range of potential key

stakeholders should be first identified in order to investigate what can be achieved in terms of sustainability by their participation in land reuse. Subsequently, the objectives-led model is devised, which relates to the development of several precise sustainability objectives, deduced from a sound knowledge of the state of the art, regarding the economic, social and environmental systems (see Table 7).

Table 7: Sustainability objectives to be met in brown-field developments (Source: Williams & Dair, 2007)

Economic sustainability objectives
1. To enable businesses to be efficient and competitive
2. To support local economic diversity
3. To provide employment opportunities
Social sustainability objectives
1. To adhere to ethical standards during the development process
2. To provide adequate local services and facilities to serve the development
3. To provide housing to meet local needs
4. To integrate the development within the locality
5. To provide high quality, liveable developments
6. To conserve local culture and heritage, if appropriate
Environmental sustainability objectives
1. To minimise the use of resources
2. To minimise pollution
3. To protect biodiversity and the natural environment

First, as far as the sustainable economic development is concerned, the perspective adopted in the model reflects the prevailing approach of the last 20 years considering the brown-field revitalisation as an opportunity to foster sustainable economic growth through the objectives spelt out within the framework. Second, the model confirms its proper assessment methodology with regard to the social issue as related to the environmental conditions; hence, the factors affecting individuals and human well-being have been considered, together with the aspects associated with the development of social capital. Third, when it comes to environmental sustainability, the brown-field redevelopment is deemed to be, according to the well developed literature, a successful strategy to restore the natural ecosystem by the implementation of the objectives set out in the model.

By taking the abovementioned criteria as a starting point, an attempt of a qualitative evaluation of the impact of innovation on brown-field redevelopment sustainability is carried out. Therefore, the empirical research, developed on a purposely selected US area, aims to apply a methodology to examine to what extent the main sustainability outcomes have been achieved, through a qualitative direct analysis.

The conceptual model is tested on a case study that has been analysed in the framework of the wider international MAPS-LED Project, designed to investigate the spatial dimension of Smart Specialisation Strategies, with the purpose of exploring the key role of S3 implementation in placed-based regeneration policies. Accordingly, through a spatially-led approach, the urban dimension ability to foster knowledge dynamics promoting innovation within the Greater Boston area has been investigated. Thereby, the physical localisation of innovation within an urban territorial scale has resulted in the identification of several case

studies, among which the Boston Innovation District planning initiative has been chosen - given the outstanding implementation of an innovation-led brown-field redevelopment initiative. Therefore, this study adds an additional element to the original research, to allow a deeper understanding of how the Boston Innovation District fostered the process of brown-field revitalisation from a sustainable development perspective, with the aim to provide transferable instruments and recommendations.

The empirical analysis has been conducted with a research methodology based on a two-step approach. Initially, secondary data have been the subject of an in-depth analysis: the main urban attributes and key socio-economic indicators were collected in order to improve knowledge on the specific features of the context; in addition, qualitative planning and financial documents were gathered to retrace the urban development activities undertaken in the Boston Seaport area over the last few decades. A direct analysis of the case study, mostly based on field work and interviews, has been performed at a later stage: an active participation during meetings and events held in incubators was ensured, multiple valued visual analysis of the urban environment was carried out and supported by photographic evidence, as well as the organisation of semi-structured and informal interviews with key informants conveniently sampled. Finally, in order to test the conceptual model, each sustainability objective has been mapped on the findings of the extensive qualitative observations and data collection.

3.1 Case Study Description

The Boston Innovation District provides an outstanding case study of brown-field revitalisation project (Cohen 2014). The underused Boston's South Waterfront has been converted into a centre of knowledge economy: an urban environment that fosters innovation, collaboration, and entrepreneurship (Menino 2010b). The geographic area dates back to the 19th century when it was a hub of fast-growing industrial development, serving as home to rail yards and manufacturing companies for Boston's working port until about 1955. Successively, the development of transportation infrastructure, with the construction of the elevated Central Artery highway and the Interstate 93, made it hardly accessible, isolating the district and marking its decline. A radical change took place when the Seaport District has been integrated into Downtown Boston again, with the completion of the Big Dig project. Inspired by the successes of 22@, the world's first innovation district located in Barcelona, Mayor Thomas Menino, in the Inaugural address (2010a), announced his vision of redeveloping the large declined industrial waterfront, calling for a "more deliberate and more experimental approach" in order to create a "hub for knowledge workers and creative jobs." As in Barcelona, the Boston Innovation District has employed an economic development strategy where government operated as the regulatory and administrative gatekeeper, working collaboratively with cross-sector private enterprises to enhance the chances of succeeding and affecting such a large scale change. Key private-sector players have been personally engaged, and the public sector openly advocated for financial incentives in order to spur established companies and emerging entrepreneurs to move into the District, creating new jobs and providing tax revenues to fund public services. Hence, a dense community of innovators and entrepreneurs has been created increasing proximity and density, according to the notion that "people in clusters innovate at a quicker rate, sharing technologies and knowledge easier" (Muro & Katz 2011). In line with Brookings Institution researchers' thought, the Boston Innovation District represents a remarkable example of sustainable economic development aimed at revitalising an underutilised parcel of land. It provides a favourable environment for

the launch and growth of firms by helping entrepreneurs and investors, universities and researchers generate new findings for the market; at the same time, it fosters employment expansion through a massive job creation phenomenon densifying the employment patterns; additionally, it facilitates the repopulation of an influential urban area, encouraging a dense residential structure and strengthening mass transit.

4. CASE STUDY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The objective-led model has been used as a research tool in the case study of the Boston Seaport regeneration. An extensive analysis, carried out between April 2016 and today in the Boston metropolitan area, allowed the author to assess the brown-field redevelopment against the above mentioned criteria related to the threefold sustainability objectives. The main purpose was to advance the body of knowledge on the nexus between brown-field and innovation, by assessing the degree of sustainability achievements and giving credit to the trend that considers innovation as a comprehensive strategy that invests on the cities underutilised assets in order to boost an inclusive and sustainable growth. The findings from the investigation are summarised and discussed in the following sub-sections.

4.1 Economic sustainability objectives

The South Boston Waterfront Public Realm Plan (BRA 1999), followed by the Municipal Harbour Plan (BRA 2009), have been issued with the specific purpose of supporting businesses to be efficient and competitive through the Seaport physical environment adaptation. Specifically, the underutilised land was the planning context for the development of a 24-hour neighbourhood providing a place for business expansion, supported by an attractive open space network and a strong urban design character. Furthermore, the construction of the Central Artery Tunnel Project, the Silver Line completion, and the strengthening of the MBTA buses have been instrumental in providing a convenient system of transport infrastructure, ensuring links from the site to the main transport corridors. Another success factor for the sustainable economy of the area is represented by the willingness to welcome every kind of industries; the area is indeed characterised by a broad inclusivity of established companies and small enterprises providing a wide range of economic activities which maximise job opportunities for local workforces. “More than 5,000 new jobs have been created in the Innovation District since 2010, as over 200 startups have set up shop in the area. From software and digital marketing to manufacturing and design, the Innovation District’s young firms span a wide array of industries and business models. The support infrastructure that these young companies need to grow, including incubators and accelerators, as well as law, design, advertising, and other professional services firms, has also moved to the District, providing a healthy ecosystem for innovative companies to thrive” (TIP 2014). Moreover, to ensure an adequate accommodation for companies, maximum flexibility for the use of the buildings is assured; most of the buildings are therefore designed to accommodate different types of groups and gatherings, concept best exemplified by the District Hall (see Figure 31) and the Innovation & Design Building.

Figure 31: District Hall (Author's pictures)

4.2 Social sustainability objectives

The factors affecting individuals and human well-being, together with the aspects associated with the development of social capital are at the core of the strategic plan that identifies key actions and initiatives to transform the Seaport area into a healthy, thriving and innovative district. Expanding Opportunities stands for the citizens' vision coupled with the Mayor's priorities and research, guiding the growth of the district towards creating a liveable neighbourhood for all residents and generations to come (Image Boston 2016). At the same time, Boston Creates strives to encourage the city's arts and culture sector in order to make it more inclusive and equitable (Boston Creates 2016). The Go Boston 2030 (2015) initiative actively engages the community envisioning a bold transportation system. A high quality architectural design and a master plan well integrated with the context, capable to attract people and businesses to live, work and play, are the result of the InnovationBoston vision (BRA 2010). The liveability is achieved by a diverse and dense complement of offices, retail, restaurant, residences and entertainment uses - as highlighted by the newly conceived Seaport Square (SSDC 2017), in order to meet people's needs for education, healthcare and leisure, but also to help communities develop social capital by providing space for formal and informal social interaction. Numerous cultural and civic institutions are located in the Innovation District, including the Children's Museum and the Institute for Contemporary Art, while numbers of experimental event landscape, such as The Lawn On D and the Fan Pier Park, have been successfully realised to bring together different communities, encouraging social interaction and fostering creativity (see Figure 32)

Figure 32: Seaport District (Courtesy of BRA); Fan Pier (Author's pictures)

The Boston Innovation District also provides a mix of housing types including residents' apartments, condominiums, and micro-unit options - without ignoring the affordability issue. With the specific purpose of providing flexible housing options to meet the needs of local people and entrepreneurs, the Boston Redevelopment Authority launched the Innovation Housing Unit Experience (BRA 2010a) allowing developers to build 300 micro apartments to help young professionals collaborate more effectively; such units can be found just in the

Seaport area at buildings like Pier 4, Flats on D, Watermark Seaport and Factory 63. The efforts of meeting the growing and changing transportation needs of the Seaport, while ensuring good connections to the rest of the city led to the South Boston Waterfront Sustainable Transportation Plan (BRA 2015). The mobility and access to local services for all has been improved, relying on a development design that considers a wide range of users including children, people with disabilities and older people (BRA 2017). Furthermore, the local culture and heritage related to the historic harbour have been firmly preserved (see Figure 33), as demonstrated by the Seaport World Trade Centre, as well as the Massachusetts Port Authority efforts towards the Boston Fish Pier conservation - a social and culturally significant space that still represents the epicentre of Boston's seafood industry after more than a century; the original buildings' structures are currently home to fishing vessels and seafood processing businesses, several maritime industrial office tenants, and the Exchange Conference Center (Massport 1976). Other historic brick warehouses are equally subject to rehabilitation in order to host the headquarters of resonant companies, such as General Electric (BRA 2016).

Figure 33: Boston Fish Pier and General Electric site (Author's picture)

4.3 Environmental sustainability objectives

Minimising the use of resources and pollution throughout the life cycle of the brown-field redevelopment has been one of the main concerns of the innovation-led strategy. Indeed, with the Boston Zoning Code Article 37 (BRA 2015a), the city requires that all large-scale projects meet certain LEED certification standards. Accordingly, the Seaport District is home to several green building best practices - such as the Fraunhofer Centre, Boston Design Centre, District Hall, Waterside Place Apartments, The Boston Convention and Exhibition Centre, which awarded high LEED ratings for their commitment in minimising negative environmental impacts because of the way they were planned, designed, constructed, and managed (USGBC 2017). Compliance with the environmental sustainability objectives is ensured by the Seaport Square development project in which energy efficient building design are complemented by infrastructure encouraging people to walk and cycle, direct access to public transportation, and thoughtful consideration to open and green spaces that connect with pathways to the waterfront.

4.4 Discussing the BID innovation-led brown-field redevelopment

The nexus between brown-field and innovation district has been proven through the application of a robust and theoretically grounded objective-led model for assessing the sustainability of brown-fields redevelopment. Based on the investigation of the secondary data collected and the direct analysis performed, the planning initiatives and development

projects put in place within the Boston Innovation District have been slotted into the three sustainability dimensions, as required by the structure of the framework proposed. As illustrated above, innovation was able to physically and economically revitalise a disused post industrial landscape, creating an attractive place and a vibrant ecosystem for wide-ranging business expansions and job opportunities maximisation. Moreover, it provided adequate housing, facilities and local services to meet individuals' needs - thanks also to a fruitful collaboration with the community, fostering social capital development and contributing to residents well-being. Finally, regardless of the massive intervention, a particular attention to the use of resources and pollution minimisation has been paid, together with a thoughtful protection of the harbour as a shared natural resource. Hence, the case study proved evidence of the effectiveness of innovative-led approach in matching all the issues considered as relevant to the redevelopment of brown-fields. Useful lessons can be drawn in encouraging planners and policy-makers towards considering the role of innovation in urban regeneration initiatives targeting distressed areas, given its capability to turn an underutilised property into an economic and environmental asset that yields dividends for the entire region.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The research is grounded on the widely recognised principle that older industrial cities have to invest into their underutilised assets to become globally competitive again; therefore, the effectiveness of the “re-imagined urban areas” model has been analysed according to the objectives of sustainable brown-fields redevelopment. Thus, a purposely chosen methodology to assess the Boston Innovation District sustainability has been applied, highlighting how innovation is experimented with within a brown-field revitalisation context. This study confirms the cities current propensity to issue innovation-oriented urban policies which, in the specific case of Boston, seek to rehabilitate urban distressed areas operating as main development driver after the economic downturn.

However, some findings raise legitimate questions about transferability issues. The Boston Innovation District took shape in a geographically privileged area - the core of the historical harbour, open to the surrounding urban grid and easy to be connected and integrated with it; moreover, the Seaport area was not affected by relevant contamination problems, as well as significant social deprivation issues. Also the significant critical mass played a key role; the Greater Boston area, indeed, has been repeatedly mentioned as one of the most innovative hubs within the US context, supported by the conspicuous presence of companies, educational institutions, business incubators and accelerators that boost the innovative ecosystem. Another relevant component that might have influenced the innovation-led strategy was the strong continuity in the planning and management policies, despite a change in the local administration and the long lead times for the project implementation; as a matter of fact, the experimental framework characterised by high planning flexibility and expedited decision making keeps being the leitmotif of the intervention.

In this respect, further research studies could attempt to provide a quantitative evaluation regarding compliance of innovation with brown-fields redevelopment in terms of sustainability achievements, by creating a set of indicators to both give a weight and prioritise the objectives, so as to grade the performance, allowing the comparison with other cases. It would be also worthwhile to explore other case studies, in order to observe the potential of innovation as a driver for a sustainable economic development in brown-fields characterised

by real hazardous contamination and social decline, as well as to examine further areas where the innovation component is less ingrained in the economic structure of the city.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper is based on research realised in the scope of the MAPS-LED Project, Multidisciplinary Approach to Plan Smart specialisation strategies for Local Economic Development, founded by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 Research Programme - Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions RISE under the Grant Agreement No. 645651.

7. REFERENCES

- Adams, D., De Sousa, C. & Tiesdell, S., 2009. Brownfield Development: A Comparison of North American and British Approaches. *Urban Studies*, 47(1), pp.75–104. Available at: <http://usj.sagepub.com/content/47/1/75.short>.
- Annan, K.A., 2002. *The Secretary-General's Message on World Environment Day*, New York.
- Audretsch, D.B. & Feldman, M.P., 2003. Knowledge Spillovers and the Geography of Innovation. *Handbook of Urban and Regional Economics*, 4.
- Bacot, H., 2006. Establishing Indicators to Evaluate Brownfield Redevelopment. *Economic Development Quarterly*, 20(2), pp.142–161.
- Bartsch, C. & Collaton, E., 1997. Brownfields: Cleaning and Reusing Contaminated Properties.
- BenDor, T. & Metcalf, S., 2005. Conceptual Modeling and Dynamic Simulation of Brownfield Redevelopment. *Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference of the System Dynamics Society*, p.21.
- Bleicher, A. & Gross, M., 2010. Sustainability assessment and the revitalization of contaminated sites: operationalizing sustainable development for local problems. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 17(1), pp.57–66. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13504500903488263%5Cnhttp://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13504500903488263#.VR5k8OH8ZYU>.
- Boer, B., 1995. Institutionalising Ecologically Sustainable Development: The Roles of National, State, and Local Governments in Translating Grand Strategy Into Action. *Willamette Law Review* 307, 31, pp.342–57.
- Boschma, R., 2005. Proximity and Innovation: A Critical Assessment. *Regional Studies*, 39(1), pp.61–74.
- Boston Creates, 2016. Cultural Plan. Available at: http://plan.bostoncreates.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/BostonCreates_ExecSummary_June2016_rspdf.pdf.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 2017. Accessibility Guidelines and Checklist. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/planning/planning-initiatives/accessibility-guidelines-and-checklist>.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 2015a. Boston Zoning Code Article 37, Green Buildings, and Climate Change Preparedness Guidelines. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/getattachment/76c48774-c670-4568-8e53-74931fa09fb5>.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 2016. General Electric (GE) Headquarters Project PDA Development Plan. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/getattachment/83a7fe48-dcaf-4492-afda-c97b2870c710>.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 2010a. Innovation Housing Unit Experience.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 2010b. InnovationBoston. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/business-dev/initiatives/innovationboston/overview>.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 2009. South Boston Waterfront District. Municipal Harbor Plan Amendment. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/getattachment/95495e05-9595-4989-9b21-52930a9e57b0>.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 2015b. South Boston Waterfront Sustainable Transportation Plan. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/getattachment/f69f2335-529c-497b-b512-3c3b0830349b>.
- BRA Boston Redevelopment Authority, 1999. The Seaport Public Realm Plan. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/getattachment/6add3767-6eb3-4a06-9d2d-03dd960391ad>.
- Capello, R. & Nijkamp, P., 2002. In search of sustainable human settlements. *Ecological Economics*, 40, pp.151–155.

- Chilton, K., Schwarz, P. & Godwin, K., 2008. *Verifying the Social, Environmental, and Economic Promise of Brownfield Programs*,
- Clark, G. & Moonen, T., 2015. *Technology, Real Estate, and the Innovation Economy*,
- CMAP Chicago Metropolitan Agency for Planning, 2008. Personal communication with David Graham.
- COBRAMAN, 2009. Report about concepts and tools for Brownfield redevelopment activities. *CENTRAL EUROPE Project ICE084P4 COBRAMAN*.
- Cohen, A., 2014. *THE DEVELOPMENT OF BOSTON'S INNOVATION DISTRICT: A Case Study of Cross-Sector Collaboration and Public Entrepreneurship*,
- Dernbach, J.C., 1998. Sustainable Development as a Framework for National Governance. *Case Western Reserve Law Review*, 49(1).
- Dixon, T., Otsuka, N. & Abe, H., 2010. *Cities in Recession : Urban Regeneration in Manchester (England) and Osaka (Japan) and the Case of " Hardcore " Brownfield Sites*, Oxford Brookes University. Available at: <http://oisd.brookes.ac.uk/news/resources/REPORTDRAFTv8.pdf>.
- Dorsey, J.W., 2003. Brownfields and Greenfields: The Intersection of Sustainable Development and Environmental Stewardship. *Environmental Practice*, 5, pp.69–76.
- Elkington, J., 1998. *Cannibals with Forks: the Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business*,
- EPA Environmental Protection Agency, 1999. *A Sustainable Brownfields Model Framework*,
- EPA Environmental Protection Agency, 2012. Brownfields and Land Revitalization, Basic Information.
- EPA United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2015. Basic Information | EPA Research | EPA. <http://www3.epa.gov/pm/basic.html>. Available at: <http://www3.epa.gov/pm/basic.html>.
- Feldman, M.P., 1994. *The geography of Innovation*,
- Frank, N., 2014. *Benefits of Public Investment in Brownfield Cleanup and Redevelopment*,
- Franz, M. et al., 2006. Sustainable development and brownfield regeneration. What defines the quality of derelict land recycling? *Environmental Sciences*, 3(2), pp.135–151. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15693430600800873%5Cnhttp://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15693430600800873#.Ua2yEkAqzL8%5Cnhttp://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/15693430600800873>.
- Franz, M. & Nathanail, P., 2005. A sustainability assessment framework for brownfield regeneration. In *Sustainable Brownfield Regeneration in Europe - Improving the Quality of Derelict Land Recycling*. p. 18–30.
- Giuffrida, G., Clark, J.J. & Cross, S.E., 2015. *Putting Innovation in Place: Georgia Tech's Innovation Neighbourhood of 'Tech Square*,
- Go Boston 2030, 2015. Vision and Action Plan.
- Greenberg, M. et al., 2001. Brownfield redevelopment as a smart growth option in the United States. *Environmentalist*, 21(2), pp.129–143.
- Hemphill, L., Berry, J. & Mcgreal, S., 2004. An Indicator-based Approach to Measuring Sustainable Urban Regeneration Performance : Part 1 , Conceptual Foundations and Methodological Framework. *Urban Studies*, 41(4), pp.725–755.
- Hueting, R. & Reijnders, L., 2004. Broad sustainability contra sustainability: The proper construction of sustainability indicators. *Ecological Economics*, 50(3–4), pp.249–260.
- Image Boston, 2016. Expanding Opportunities 2030. Available at: <http://20222-presscdn.pagely.netdna-cdn.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/Ib2030-Vision-Report-WEB-2016-11-17-SPREADS.pdf>.
- Katz, B. & Wagner, J., 2014. The Rise of Innovation Districts : A New Geography of Innovation in America. *Brookings Institution*, (May), pp.1–34. Available at: <http://www.brookings.edu/~media/Programs/metro/Images/Innovation/InnovationDistricts1.pdf>.
- Knox, P.L. & McCarthy, L., 2012. *Urbanization: an introduction to urban geography* 3rd editio., Boston: Pearson Publishers.
- Massport, 1976. Boston Fish Pier Feasibility Study.
- Menino, T., 2010a. Inaugural Address.
- Menino, T., 2010b. Panel Comments, Florence. Available at: <http://www.innovationdistrict.org/2010/12/02/ciao-innovation-district-menino-shares- bostons-innovation-agenda-in-italy>.
- Montini, L., 2014. 3 Types of Thriving “Innovation Districts” in America. *Inc*.
- Muro, M. & Katz, B., 2011. The New Cluster Moment: How Regional Innovation Clusters can Foster the Next Economy. *Entrepreneurship and Global Competitiveness in Regional Economies: Determinants and Policy Implications*, 22, pp.93–140. Available at: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/S1048-4736\(2011\)0000022008](http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/S1048-4736(2011)0000022008).
- Nijkamp, P., Rodenburg, C. a & Wagtendonk, A.J., 2002. Success factors for sustainable urban brownfield development. *Ecological Economics*, 40(2), pp.235–252. Available at: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921800901002567>.

- Olivier, L. et al., 2005. The scale and nature of European brownfields. In *International Conference on Managing Urban Land LQM Ltd, Nottingham, UK, Belfast, Northern Ireland, UK*. p. Available at: <http://www.cabernet.org.uk/resourcef>.
- Olsson, J., 2009. Sustainable development from below: institutionalising a global idea-complex. *Local Environment*, 14(2), pp.127–138. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13549830802521436>.
- PCSD President's Council on Sustainable Development, 1998. *Sustainable America: A New Consensus for Prosperity, Opportunity, and a Healthy Environment for the Future*,
- Pediaditi, K., Wehrmeyer, W. & Chenoweth, J., 2005. Monitoring the sustainability of Brownfield redevelopment projects. The Redevelopment Assessment Framework (RAF). *Land Contamination & Reclamation*, 13(2), pp.173–183.
- Preston, M., 2003. Greening brownfields. *American City & Issue*, 118 12, p.p26, 1p, 1c.
- Read, D.C., 2016. *Case Studies in Innovation District Planning and Development*,
- RESCUE Regeneration of European Sites in Cities and Urban Environment Report, 2003. *Development of an Analytical Sustainability Framework for the Context of Brownfield Regeneration in France, Germany, Poland and the United Kingdom. Final Report of Work Package 1.*, Available at: http://www.rescue-europe.com/download/reports/1_Analytical_sustainability_framework.pdf.
- Ruthl, J.B., 1998. The Seven Degrees of Relevance: Why Should Real World Environmental Attorneys Care Now About Sustainable Development Policy? 8 *DUKE ENVTL. L. & POL'Y F.* 273, 288 n.46.
- Sardinha, I.D., Craveiro, D. & Milheiras, S., 2013. A sustainability framework for redevelopment of rural brownfields: stakeholder participation at SÃO DOMINGOS mine, Portugal. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 57, pp.200–208.
- Sassen, S., 1991. *The global city*, Available at: <https://op.kulib.kyoto-u.ac.jp/webopac/catdbi.do?pkey=BB02333006>.
- Schädler, S. et al., 2011. Designing sustainable and economically attractive brownfield revitalization options using an integrated assessment model. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92(3), pp.827–837.
- Seaport Square Development Company LLC, 2017. Seaport Square. Available at: <http://www.bostonplans.org/getattachment/8005ea79-e8dd-40d8-82b8-ada0d7daa442>.
- Sirmans, S. & Macpherson, D., 2003. The state of affordable housing. *Journal of Real Estate Literature*, 11, pp.133–155. Available at: <http://ares.metapress.com/index/V417570582656112.pdf>.
- TIP The Intersector Project, 2014. *THE DEVELOPMENT OF BOSTON'S INNOVATION DISTRICT: A Case Study of Cross-Sector Collaboration and Public Entrepreneurship*,
- United Nations, 1992a. Agenda 21. *United Nations Conference on Environment & Development*, (June), p.351. Available at: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/index.php?page=view&nr=23&type=400>.
- United Nations, 1992b. Rio Declaration on Environment and Development. *Environmental Conservation*, 19(4), p.366.
- US Conference of Mayors, 2008. *Recycling America's Land. A National Report on Brownfield Redevelopment*,
- USGBC U.S. Green Building Council, 2017. LEED Projects. Available at: <http://www.usgbc.org/projects>.
- Verbit, S.R., 2001. New Law May Unlock Potential for Brownfields. *Environmental Protection*, 12(8), pp.31–33.
- Wedding, G.C. & Crawford-Brown, D., 2007. Measuring site-level success in brownfield redevelopments: A focus on sustainability and green building. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 85(2), pp.483–495.
- Williams, K. & Dair, C., 2007. A Framework for Assessing the Sustainability of Brownfield Developments. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 50(1), pp.23–40.
- World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987. *Our Common Future*, Available at: <http://www.un-documents.net/wced-ocf.htm>.
- Worrall, R. et al., 2009. Towards a sustainability criteria and indicators framework for legacy mine land. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 17(16), pp.1426–1434.